

4. V. D. N. BASTRY and T. R. SESHADRI, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 262.
5. H. G. KRISHNAMURTY and T. R. SESHADRI, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 151.
6. TIAN-SHUNG WU, CHENG-SHENG KUOH, SHIEN-TSUNG HO, KEI-SHIEU YANG and KONG-KO LEE, *Phytochemistry*, 1981, 20, 527.

Synthesis and Screening of Some 4(5)-Arylhydrazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones

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A number of compounds having imidazole nucleus substituted at positions 1, 2 and 5 possess good therapeutic effects¹⁻³. Recently, some 2-mercapto benzoyl imidazoles have been found to exhibit pronounced fungicidal and amoebicidal properties⁴⁻⁶. A large number of hydrazones⁷⁻⁹ have also shown significant amoebicidal activities. Considering the importance of imidazole moiety and hydrazone group, we have synthesised some 4(5)-arylhydrazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethiones and evaluated them for amoebicidal and fungicidal properties *in vitro*.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected.

α -Phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde hydrochloride (II): Ethyl- γ -phthalamido- α, β -dioxobutarate- α -phenylhydrazone¹⁰ (I) (11.2 g; 0.04 mole) was heated with 30% hydrochloric acid (150 ml) till a clear solution was obtained. On cooling, most of the phthalic acid separated, was filtered off and discarded. The filtrate was concentrated to the

half of the total volume on a water bath and chilled in ice. Precipitated phthalic acid was again filtered off. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. A highly hygroscopic hydrochloride of α -phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde, m.p. 150°, was obtained. (Found: C, 50.38; H, 5.40. C₉H₁₂ON₃Cl requires C, 50.58; H, 5.62%).

In case of other compounds, the hydrochloride in solution was taken for the next reaction.

4(5)-Arylhydrazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione (III): α -Phenylhydrazone- γ -aminopurvaldehyde (II) (4.27 g; 0.02 mole) was dissolved in water (100 ml), potassium thiocyanate (1.94 g; 0.02 mole) dissolved in water (10 ml) was added and the mixture heated on a water bath for 2 hr and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in warm water (50 ml) and treated with a saturated solution of mercuric acetate till the formation of yellow precipitate was complete. The precipitate was suspended in water (50 ml) and made acidic with dilute HCl. H₂S gas was passed to precipitate mercury sulphide which was filtered off and the filtrate was treated with animal charcoal and evaporated to dryness to obtain the hydrochloride of 4(5)-arylhydrazonomethylenyl-2(3H)-imidazolethione as a yellow hygroscopic substance. The hydrochloride was dissolved in dry ethanol and neutralised with ethyl alcohol and potassium hydroxide mixture. Precipitated potassium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to crystallisation.

Purity of the synthesised compounds was tested by tlc using 50% ethanol as eluent and silica gel as adsorbent on the glass plate with iodine as indicator, when only one spot was observed. These compounds can exist in azo or hydrazone form. Wiley and Jorboe¹¹ confirmed from ir and uv data that the hydrazone form is more stable. Relevant data regarding compounds (III) are given in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening:

Determination of amoebicidal activity¹²: All the synthesised compounds were tested for their amoebicidal activity.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND AMOEBICIDAL ACTIVITY OF 4(5)-ARYLHYDRAZONOMETHYLENYL-2(3H)-IMIDAZOLETHIONES

Compound No.	Molecular formula*	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Amoebicidal activity at the minimum inhibitory concentration of	
					1000 μ g/ml	500 μ g/ml
IV	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	H	228	20	+	+
V	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	248	28	-	±
VI	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	264	20	-	-
VII	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	269	24	-	+
VIII	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -OH	245	28	-	-
IX	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ S	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	290	35	+	+
X	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>p</i> -Cl	232	26	-	+
XI	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>m</i> -Cl	224	24	+	+
XII	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SOCl	<i>o</i> -Cl	240	24.5	-	+
XIII	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅	259	33	-	±

*Carbon and Hydrogen analysis was found satisfactory.

(-) = Negative culture, (+) = Positive culture, (±) = Living culture and dead amoebae.

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bicidal activity against an axenic culture of *E. histolytica*.

Determination of fungicidal activity¹⁸ :

Four fungi, *A. terreus*, *A. nidulans*, *A. niger* and *A. flavus* were used in the present study.

Sabour's broth (peptone 10.0 g/l, dextrose 20.0 g/l, pH ~6.0) was used as test medium. The compounds were dissolved in alcohol and 1.0 ml of test solution (100 µg/ml) was added to 1 ml of medium in each tube. The tubes were inoculated and incubated at 26 ± 2° for 7 days. The vegetative growth was recorded visually in each case (Table 2).

Results and Discussion

Compound nos. V, VI, VII, VIII, X, XII and XIII show amoebicidal activity at 1 : 1000 dilution, whereas compound nos. VI and VIII show good and

V and XIII show slight amoebicidal activity at 1 : 500 dilution (Table 1). Compound nos. VI, VII, X, XII and XIII show good fungicidal activity (Table 2).

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References

1. P. MELLONI, E. DRADI and W. LONGMANN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 926.
2. C. COSAN, R. CRISEN, R. N. HORCLOIS and J. J. ROBERT, *Az. Foraus*, 1966, **16**, 23.
3. R. RAFAUR and V. SUNFIE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 794.
4. R. C. GUPTA, R. NATH, K. SHANKER, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHORE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 434.
5. AKHTAR ALI and R. K. SAKSENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 417.
6. AKHTAR ALI and R. K. SAKSENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 420.
7. SYDNEY ARCHER, *U. S. Patent*, 3, 365, 458, 23 Jan. 1968; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, **69**, 27458.
8. A. E. SURREY and J. R. MEYER, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1961, **3**, 409, 419.
9. E. MESSARANI, D. MARDI, S. ROSSI and L. DEGAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 685.
10. R. K. SAKSENA and S. D. VERMA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1970, **39**, 279.
11. R. H. WILEY and C. H. JARBOE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **77**, 403.
12. B. N. SINGH, S. R. DAS and G. P. DUTTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, **42**, 227.
13. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, S. N. BHATTACHARYA, J. DASGUPTA and S. K. TANDON, *Indian J. Microbiol.*, 1968, **8**, 65.

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL SCREENING OF 4(5)-ARYLHYDRAZONOMETHYLENYL-2(3H)-IMIDAZOLETHIONES

Compound No.	<i>A. terreus</i>	<i>A. nidulans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
Control	++++	++++	++++	++++
IV	++	++	+	-
V	++	+++	+++	++++
VI	-	-	±	+
VII	-	-	+	±
VIII	+	+	+	+
IX	+++	+++	+++	+++
X	-	+	+	-
XI	++	++	+	+
XII	-	+	-	±
XIII	++	-	±	-

++ to ++++ = Good growth, positive utilisation and no fungal activity.

± to ++ = Slight growth, slight fungicidal activity.

- = No growth, fungicidal activity.